

THE ROLE OF COLORS IN PEOPLE'S LIFE

Omonov Davronbek Alisher ugli

Teacher of the Department of Fine Arts, Fergana State University

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Abstract. *The article talks about the world of psychology. It talks about the influence of colors on human logic and their role in our lifestyle. It is possible to heal people through cleansing and learn about the way people create things.*

Keywords: *color, harmony, achromatic and chromatic, colorful, symbol.*

Introduction. The harmony of different colors in works of fine art, the interrelationship between beautiful color combinations, the leading color in the work of art is called color, and color mixtures occupy an important place in the painting. The colors are close to each other. colors blend together.

The current conditions in our country require a review of the form, content and mechanisms of training and the introduction of appropriate changes to this process. In particular, in these days, in order to implement measures aimed at improving the system of pre-school education, there was a need to improve the content and forms of training of educators.

Decree No. PQ-2707 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 2016 "On measures to further improve the preschool education system in 2017-2021", September 30, 2017 "Measures to radically improve the management of the preschool education system" Decree No. PF-5198, dated September 9, 2017, Decision No. PQ-3261, dated September 9, 2017, "On Measures to Fundamentally Improve the Preschool Education System", as well as the Decree of the Ministry of Preschool Education dated June 18, 2018 Implementation of the State curriculum of the preschool educational institution "Ilk Kadam" No. 1 "State requirements for the development of children of primary and preschool age" and, on this basis, improving the content of the processes of raising the qualifications of educators of preschool educational institutions and regularly improving their professional competence refers to increase.

The purpose of preschool education is to prepare children for school education, to form a child as a healthy, developed, independent person, to reveal his creative abilities, to ensure his readiness for study, systematic education, and to cultivate enthusiasm for this process.

Article 11 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" states: "This education is carried out in families, kindergartens and other educational institutions, regardless of the form of ownership, until the age of 6-7." In fact, the earlier the education starts, the earlier its effect will be manifested and it will have a positive effect on the whole way of life of a person.

Tasks performed on the application in "visual activity" classes are of great importance in the education and upbringing of children of preschool age, encouraging them to develop their personal qualities, psychological and aesthetic abilities.

The use of various techniques and various artistic, natural and discarded materials interesting for children in the "Visual activity" classes in preschool educational institutions further enriches the content of the application classes. In the process of drawing in the application technology in the "visual activity" classes, children:

- education of artistic taste;
- development of practical artistic activities and skills;

- development of idea, creative thinking and imagination, perception;
- development of accurate hand movements and fine motor skills of fingers;
- Educational and educational issues such as creating an opportunity for the budding of professional artistic and creative activity are solved.

The future of our republic is directly related to the development of science, creativity, and education.

Therefore, in the development of creative abilities of children of preschool age, natural and discarded materials are of educational and educational importance, along with various artistic materials, in the "Visual activity" classes. After all, nature is the oldest and richest source of beauty. Taking into account this factor, the issues of artistic-aesthetic education and environmental education are discussed in the "Visual activity" classes using the application technology of objects, items and objects, using natural, artistic and abandoned materials in their place to enrich the content of the classes, using various techniques in an integrative way. special attention was paid to the description.

Natural materials, as well as various artistic materials, have their own didactic capabilities in the development of creative qualities and image skills in preschool children's visual activities.

From the analysis of the structure and content of the basic program "Bolajon" developed for pre-school educational institutions, it is clear that, starting from small groups, the most time is allocated to visual activities, physical education and music (2 hours each). If we add other types of visual activity - application (0.5 hours), construction (0.5 hours) and clay work (1 hour), the total is 4 hours. If we take into account that the weekly load is 12 hours, visual activity makes up one third of all activities. Therefore, visual activity is the largest department that acquires integrative content and is carried out in a logical and didactic connection with other types of activity. This factor also means that it is necessary to improve the content and methodology of visual activity classes in harmony with other types of activity.

During the next 8-10 years, all directions of preschool education were implemented on the basis of the "Child of the Third Millennium" program. By 2010, the State educational standards of general secondary education and the State requirements of extracurricular education were improved, and the content of education was further facilitated. This factor required the implementation of certain activities even at the pre-school stage of the continuous education system. Based on this socio-pedagogical need, the State requirements of preschool education were improved, and the educational process in preschool educational institutions was implemented based on the "Bolajon" basic program developed according to the updated content.

"Painting", "Working with plasticine (clay)", "Application" and "Building-making" trainings are given as a separate section in the "Visual activity" training system. As the main task of the classes, it was specially noted that by teaching children of preschool age to describe the observed events and objects, forming and developing imaginations about the environment, to know the world and to understand the realities in it, by means of visual activity. In order to carry out these educational actions effectively, it is necessary to have a set of educational and methodical literature developed on the basis of modern conditions and needs for educators of preschool educational institutions. The results of experiments, observations, and their analysis show that there is a socio-pedagogical demand and need in this area, as well as that methodological developments that acquire modern content and essence have not been created for visual activities for preschool educational institutions up to 7 years old in harmony with the educational reforms

implemented in our country in the following years. shows. Some of the developments published by some methodists and pedagogic scientists require the creation of manuals with a new content that meet the requirements of the time due to the fact that they are not in circulation and are not able to meet today's social requirements. Therefore, the creation of a set of methodical developments on visual activities for all groups of preschool education remains an urgent problem.

The visual activity of preschool children is considered the most popular type, and almost all children like to draw. But they may not be able to draw well as required.

The world is full of mysteries. It can be symbolically compared to the work of the artist "Black Square". After all, "square" means its literary creation, four sides - a symbol of infinity, and "black color" indicates that abstraction is an incomprehensible secret of all the mysteries of the world. No matter how much humanity tries to know these secrets, it is natural that its thinking is weak. In the end, you will come to the philosophical conclusion that a person needs an infinite lifetime to learn these miracles.

As we observe existence, we are amazed to see that the world around us consists of different colors. "How much meaning lies in these colors?" - you go home. Our ancestors were amazed by this mysterious world of nature and have been studying it for centuries. Our holy book "Holy Qur'an" also expresses the following philosophical thoughts about the miracles of color: "Is there a color giver more beautiful than Allah?" or "... haven't you seen that we grow fruits of different colors?!", and "... the mountains have white, red, colorful stripes, and pitch black"². "Also, among humans, animals and domestic animals, there are different colors"³.

Each color means a person. "Why is nature made green?" What is the reason for this? What does it mean if nature is red or yellow? What colors raise a person's mood? Which one has a negative or positive effect? Is it possible to determine the health of people or animals through their colors?"

The source of light in nature is the sun, and its light is a very complex light. The English scientist Isaac Newton first experimented in his laboratory by passing sunlight through a triangular glass prism and observed that it appeared on the screen in several colors. The scientist sent sunlight through a small hole in a dark room and found out that when the light is passed through a three-sided glass prism, the colors of the spectrum are formed on the surface of the screen. The least refracted bottom of the colors formed on the screen surface is red, and the most refracted is violet, and there is no definite boundary between the color bands, each color gradually -slowly changes and sees a band of golden, yellow, green, airy, blue colors.

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Existing colors in nature can be divided into two parts: achromatic¹ and chromatic colors. White gray and black colors and all the colors formed by mixing them in different proportions are called achromatic colors. There are no achromatic colors in the spectrum.

For centuries, our ancestors and scientists have been conducting research and experiments at a certain level. Currently, even in some developed countries, special color institutes and scientific laboratories are working effectively in this regard. In this place, it is possible to highlight the world-famous color institute in Tokyo, Japan.

Major scientists use color to "speak" in a symbolic sense, to treat and educate people by means of colors, to think philosophically through colors, to understand the inner world of people through colors, as well as to increase the agricultural productivity of colors, in economy and other fields. researches are being conducted on the position of positive problem solving.

Our ancestors left us a lot of spiritual treasures about color and its place in human life, healing, educational, philosophical and spiritual aspects. Unfortunately, we cannot fully use this spiritual heritage. For example, in education and training, medicine, technology, agriculture, economy and other fields, these issues are not emphasized enough. However, in the developed countries of the world, great importance is attached to the place of colors in human life.

It is known that the education system teaches color science. However, there are not enough textbooks, manuals, electronic versions, etc. that meet the requirements of the present time. Almost no scientific research work has been conducted on the teaching methodology of color image science.

If we refer to the spiritual heritage left by our ancestors from the types of applied arts, every item or decoration has its shape, color and size. For example, the color of that decoration has a different effect on the human psyche, these colors have their own symbolic meaning and healing properties. Therefore, it is necessary for the future master of applied art to study the science of color and image in depth and comprehensively.

It would not be wrong to say that learning the rules, methods and technology of painting is one of the most important tasks. It is natural that knowledge about achromatic and chromatic colors is included among such prerequisites.

All colors in nature that can be seen by our eyes can be conventionally divided into two: achromatic and chromatic colors. Colors from white to dark black are achromatic colors (white, gray, black, black, jet black) and the rest are chromatic colors (red, yellow, blue, etc.).

It is a very difficult task to correctly perform the naturalness of colors in the image. This can be achieved through hard work, fine taste and excellent observation. It is especially important to depict a still life in one color in order to learn to distinguish the degrees of hunger and satiety of things in a still life, to understand the unity of color in it. Painting in this way makes it much easier to move on to color rendering of difficult still lifes later.

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